

Assessment of Anthropometric Measurement of Stature and Upper Limb of Adult Male Santals in Comparison with Bangalis

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ABSTRACT

Background: Anthropometric measurements of upper limb segments are useful for ethnic comparison and stature estimation. Santals are one of the largest indigenous groups in Bangladesh, but limited data exist on their upper limb anthropometry compared to the mainstream Bangali population. **Objective:** To compare stature and upper limb measurements between adult male Santals and Bangalis and assess the correlation between measured and estimated stature using multiplication factors. **Methods & Materials:** This cross-sectional study was conducted from January to December 2017 in the Department of Anatomy, Rangpur Medical College, on 100 adults male Santals and 100 Bangalis aged 20-45 years from Kaharol upazilla, Dinajpur, Bangladesh. Measurements included stature, weight, upper limb segments, hand breadth, mid-upper arm circumference, and forearm girth. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 16.0. **Results:** Forearm length was significantly longer in Santals ($p=0.029$), while weight ($p=0.025$) and forearm girth ($p=0.000$) were higher in Bangalis. Stature, arm length, hand length, and BMI showed no significant differences. Multiplication factors for total upper limb length, arm length, forearm length, and third finger length were significantly lower in Santals ($p<0.01$). Total upper limb length showed the strongest correlation with measured stature in both groups ($R=0.847$ for Santals, $R=0.719$ for Bangalis). **Conclusion:** Santal males have longer forearmed relative to stature than Bangali males. Upper limb segments can reliably estimate stature in both populations, with total upper limb length being the best predictor.

Keywords: Adult male, Anthropometry, Bangladesh, Ethnic comparison, Forearm length, Santal, Stature estimation, Upper limb

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INTRODUCTION

Anthropometry, the scientific measurement of human body parts, serves as a fundamental tool in describing morphological characteristics, assessing nutritional status, and establishing individual biological profiles [1]. Among various anthropometric parameters, stature represents a key biological variable that correlates systematically with other body segments due to proportional biological relationships established during growth and development [2]. The relationship between stature and upper limb segments has received particular attention in forensic anthropology, as these measurements enable stature estimation when complete remains are unavailable [3,4]. Stature estimation from upper limb measurements has been extensively studied across diverse populations. Significant positive correlations have been demonstrated between stature and all upper limb measurements in an Egyptian population, with regression models providing accurate stature prediction [1]. Strong correlations between stature and upper limb length ($r=0.89$) and hand length ($r=0.78$) have been reported among Iranian adults, concluding that upper limb length provides better stature prediction than hand measurements alone [5]. Research on Korean populations has further validated these relationships,

with ulna length showing the highest coefficient of determination for stature estimation [2]. A study on the Han population of southern China confirmed that upper extremity dimensions significantly correlate with stature, though lower limb measurements generally provide better estimates [6]. Ethnic variation in body dimensions necessitates population-specific standards for stature estimation, as formulas derived from one population may not apply to others due to different hereditary and environmental conditions [3,7]. Hand morphology, including hand length, breadth, and derived indices, exhibits considerable ethnic and sexual dimorphism [8]. The hand index, calculated as $(\text{hand breadth}/\text{hand length}) \times 100$, classifies hand shapes and serves as an ethnic marker [9]. Studies on Indian populations have documented significant variation in hand proportions among different ethnic groups, emphasizing the need for population-specific reference data [4,10]. Body mass index (BMI), calculated from weight and stature, remains the most widely used indicator of nutritional status. Mid-upper arm circumference (MUAC) provides an additional, quick assessment of muscle mass and fat reserves, particularly useful in field settings [11]. Forearm girth has also been explored as a nutritional indicator, though population-specific reference values

remain limited [12]. Santals constitute one of the largest indigenous communities in Bangladesh, residing primarily in the northern districts. While anecdotal observations suggest that Santals possess longer upper limbs relative to their stature, no systematic anthropometric data exist to support this claim [13]. The absence of such data limits accurate stature estimation in forensic contexts and hinders understanding of ethnic morphological variation within Bangladesh. Therefore, this study was undertaken to document anthropometric parameters of stature and upper limb segments in adult male Santals, compare them with adult male Bangalis, and assess the utility of upper limb segments in stature estimation.

METHODS & MATERIALS

This cross-sectional analytical study was conducted from January to December 2017 in the Department of Anatomy, Rangpur Medical College, Bangladesh. A total of 200 adult males were enrolled, comprising 100 Santals and 100 Bangalis, recruited from different villages of Kaharol upazilla, Dinajpur district.

Inclusion criteria: Participants were Bangladeshi nationals aged 20 to 45 years, right-handed, and engaged as day laborers

or farmers to ensure similar socioeconomic status.

Exclusion criteria: Individuals with mixed ethnic origin, amputated lower limb, musculoskeletal disorders affecting stature or limb growth, congenital or acquired limb deformities, and those unwilling to provide written informed consent were excluded.

Study procedure: Stature was measured using a stadiometer and weight using a digital weighing machine. Total upper limb length, arm length, and forearm length were measured with a steel tape. Palm length, third finger length, and hand breadth were measured with a digital sliding caliper. Mid-upper arm circumference and forearm girth

were measured using a flexible measuring tape. All measurements were taken on the left upper limb twice, and the average was recorded. Multiplication factors were calculated as stature divided by each upper limb segment length.

Data analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 16.0. Unpaired t-test compared Santals and Bangalis. Paired t-test compared measured and estimated stature. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULT

A total of 200 adult males (100 Santals and 100 Bangalis) aged 20 to 45 years participated in this study. The mean age of

Santals was 28.18 ± 6.14 years, and that of Bangalis was 29.93 ± 6.12 years, with no significant difference between groups ($p = 0.058$). Regarding general anthropometric parameters, the mean stature of Santals (162.38 ± 6.18 cm) was slightly lower than that of Bangalis (163.79 ± 5.14 cm), but the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.082$). However, mean weight was significantly lower in Santals (55.24 ± 8.02 kg) compared to Bangalis (57.85 ± 8.28 kg, $p = 0.025$). Body mass index was also lower in Santals (20.95 ± 2.72 kg/m²) than in Bangalis (21.53 ± 2.68 kg/m²), though this difference did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.126$) *Table I*.

Table I

Comparison of general anthropometric parameters between Santals and Bangalis.

Parameter	Santal (n=100)	Bangali (n=100)	p-value
Age (years)	28.18 ± 6.14	29.93 ± 6.12	0.058
Stature (cm)	162.38 ± 6.18	163.79 ± 5.14	0.082
Weight (kg)	55.24 ± 8.02	57.85 ± 8.28	0.025
BMI (kg/m ²)	20.95 ± 2.72	21.53 ± 2.68	0.126

Data analysis: Unpaired t-test; p < 0.05 considered significant

Comparison of upper limb segment lengths revealed that forearm length was significantly longer in Santals (25.29 ± 1.25

cm) than in Bangalis (24.91 ± 1.18 cm, $p = 0.029$). Total upper limb length, arm length, hand length, palm length, third

finger length, and hand breadth showed no significant differences between groups ($p > 0.05$ for all) *Table II*.

Table II

Comparison of upper limb segment lengths (cm) between Santals and Bangalis.

Variable	Santal	Bangali	p-value
Total upper limb length	71.13 ± 3.24	70.64 ± 2.45	0.233
Arm length	28.78 ± 1.62	28.57 ± 1.35	0.314
Forearm length	25.29 ± 1.25	24.91 ± 1.18	0.029
Hand length	18.49 ± 0.91	18.54 ± 0.72	0.693
Hand breadth	8.22 ± 0.43	8.32 ± 0.39	0.078

Data analysis: Unpaired t-test; p < 0.05 considered significant.

Mid-upper arm circumference was slightly lower in Santals (27.19 ± 2.20 cm) than in Bangalis (27.61 ± 2.07 cm, $p = 0.160$), but forearm girth was significantly lower in

Santals (24.37 ± 1.21 cm) compared to Bangalis (25.05 ± 1.40 cm, $p = 0.000$). Hand index values classified both groups predominantly as mesocheiri (medium hand

shape), with 54% of Santals and 59% of Bangalis falling into this category *Table III*.

Table III

Comparison of MUAC, forearm girth, hand index, and hand types.

Variable	Santal	Bangali	p-value
MUAC (cm)	27.19 ± 2.20	27.61 ± 2.07	0.160
Forearm girth (cm)	24.37 ± 1.21	25.05 ± 1.40	0.000
Hand index	44.49 ± 2.18	44.90 ± 1.81	0.144
Mesocheiri hand type (%)	54 (54%)	59 (59%)	-

Data analysis: Unpaired t-test for continuous variables; p < 0.05 considered significant.

Multiplication factors for total upper limb length, arm length, forearm length, and third finger length were significantly lower in

Santals than in Bangalis ($p < 0.01$ for all), indicating that Santals have longer upper

limb segments relative to their stature (*Table IV*).

Table IV

Comparison of multiplication factors between Santals and Bangalis.

Multiplication factor for	Santal	Bangali	p-value
Total upper limb length	2.28 ± 0.05	2.32 ± 0.06	0.000
Arm length	5.65 ± 0.20	5.74 ± 0.22	0.003
Forearm length	6.43 ± 0.24	6.58 ± 0.26	0.000
Hand length	8.79 ± 0.33	8.84 ± 0.29	0.244

Data analysis: Unpaired t-test; p < 0.05 considered significant.

Figure 1 Bar diagram showing forearm length distribution of adult male Santals and Bangalis.

Figure 1 showing forearm length distribution of adult male Santals and Bangalis.

Figure 2: The curve shows the correlation between measured stature and estimated stature for total upper limb length. Figure.

A shows the value of adult male Santal, and Figure B shows the value of adult male Bangali, MSTATURE = Measured stature, ESTAL = Estimated stature of total upper limb length (Figure 2).

DISCUSSION

The present study compared stature and upper limb anthropometric measurements between adult male Santals and Bangalis from Dinajpur, Bangladesh. The findings reveal significant ethnic differences in specific upper limb segments, particularly forearm length, despite similar stature between groups. The mean stature of Santals (162.38 cm) was slightly but not significantly lower than that of Bangalis (163.79 cm). This finding contrasts with previous reports suggesting that indigenous populations often have shorter stature than mainstream populations [1,14]. A study on

Indian tribal populations reported mean statures ranging from 158.5 to 161.2 cm among adult males, which are comparable to the Santal values in the present study [14]. The absence of a significant stature difference may be attributed to similar socioeconomic status (both groups were day laborers or farmers) and nutritional conditions in the study area [6,15]. Forearm length emerged as the only upper limb segment showing a significant ethnic difference, with Santals having longer forearms (25.29 cm vs. 24.91 cm, p=0.029). This finding supports the observation that Santals possess relatively longer upper limbs compared to their stature [13]. Similar findings have been reported in other warm-climate populations, where longer extremities facilitate heat dissipation [16,17]. The significantly lower multiplication factors for total upper limb length, arm

length, forearm length, and third finger length in Santals (p<0.01) further confirm that these segments are longer relative to stature. This proportional difference may represent an adaptive trait to the hot and humid environment of northern Bangladesh [16]. Weight and forearm girth were significantly higher in Bangalis (p=0.025 and p=0.000, respectively). These differences likely reflect nutritional status rather than genetic factors, as both groups shared similar occupational backgrounds [11,15]. The mean BMI of both groups fell within the normal range (18.50-25.00 kg/m²), though Santals had a lower mean BMI (20.95 vs. 21.53) and a wider distribution, including underweight categories. This finding aligns with reports of higher underweight prevalence among indigenous populations in South Asia [15,18]. The significantly lower forearm girth in

Santals, even after controlling for occupation, suggests possible chronic energy deficiency, which warrants further nutritional investigation [12]. Hand index values classified both groups as mesocheiri (medium hand shape), consistent with findings from other South Asian populations [9,19]. The predominance of mesocheiri hand type (54% in Santals, 59% in Bangalis) indicates similar hand morphology patterns between these ethnic groups, despite other anthropometric differences [8,20]. This similarity suggests that hand shape may be less sensitive to ethnic variation than limb segment proportions [21]. Regarding stature estimation, total upper limb length showed the strongest correlation with measured stature in both groups ($R=0.847$ for Santals, $R=0.719$ for Bangalis). These correlation coefficients are comparable to those reported in Egyptian ($R=0.81-0.89$) and Iranian ($R=0.89$) populations [1,5]. The higher correlation in Santals may reflect less variability in body proportions within this ethnically homogeneous group [3,22]. The significant correlations for all upper limb segments confirm that these measurements can reliably estimate stature in both populations, consistent with previous studies on Korean and Chinese populations [2,6]. The lower multiplication factors in Santals indicate that using Bangali-derived formulas for stature estimation would overestimate stature in Santals [23,24]. This finding emphasizes the need for population-specific regression equations when applying anthropometric methods across ethnic groups [3,25]. The study has several limitations. The sample was limited to a single district (Dinajpur) and may not represent all Santal or Bangali populations in Bangladesh. Only adult males were included, limiting generalizability to females and other age groups. The cross-sectional design precludes assessment of secular trends in body dimensions.

LIMITATIONS

The study was limited to adult males from a single district, restricting generalizability to females, other age groups, and different regions. The cross-sectional design and relatively small sample size are additional constraints.

CONCLUSION

Adult male Santals have significantly longer forearm length relative to stature compared to Bangalis, despite similar mean stature. Weight and forearm girth are significantly higher in Bangalis, suggesting better nutritional status. Upper limb segments, particularly total upper limb length, show strong correlation with measured stature in

both groups, supporting their utility for stature estimation in forensic and anthropological contexts. Population-specific standards are recommended for accurate application across ethnic groups in Bangladesh.

RECOMMENDATION

Future studies should include females, other age groups, and multiple regions across Bangladesh. Longitudinal designs and larger sample sizes are recommended. Development of population-specific regression equations for stature estimation from upper limb segments is also advised.

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